

RESIN TREATMENT FOR RELIABLE TRANSVERSE SHEAR STRENGTH ASSESSMENT IN AEROSPACE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Interlaminar transverse shear strength testing is usually part of the extensive certification process of large aerospace structures. These tests are performed on small scale specimens with exposed free edges, which are often non-existent in the final large scale product. Stress concentrations at the free edges lead to initiation and propagation of delaminations, resulting in premature failure of the specimens. The tests become over-conservative and the transverse shear strength of the final product is significantly under-predicted. In this work, a resin treatment is applied on the edges of short beam specimens resulting in a 28% increase in transverse shear strength. The treatment suppresses stress concentrations in the vicinity of the free edges and can be used in the certification process of aerospace structures to produce less conservative transverse shear strength predictions, without significant additional costs. The effects of the treatment are analysed in detail using experiments, computed-tomography (CT) and finite element analysis (FEA).

1 INTRODUCTION

The design and certification process of large aerospace components heavily relies on extensive testing of small scale specimens with exposed free edges. Due to the mismatch in elastic properties across plies in carbon-fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates, high transverse stresses develop at the ply interfaces in the vicinity of these free edges so that boundary conditions between adjacent laminae can be verified.

The increase in transverse inter-laminar stresses usually causes delaminations starting from the free edge. Testing becomes over-conservative and leads to inaccurate predictions of the actual strength of the final large scale product, where the free edge effects are either mitigated in the case of a wide part or completely removed in case the structure is built into surrounding components.

Different strategies have been proposed to reduce the edge effect, such as the use of thin adhesive layers [1] and using caps which are bonded onto the free edges [2]. Some of these have limitations, with the former, for instance, only being applicable to in-plane loading tests and the latter only reducing inter-laminar normal stress but not shear stress. Other techniques have been suggested, such as applying a resin treatment on the free edges of the laminate. This approach can be used in out-of-plane loading conditions and has been previously introduced in [3] for 4-point bending tests of curved laminates, successfully reducing all inter-laminar transverse stress components near the edge.

In this work, the resin treatment was applied on the free edges of short beam shear specimens of a quasi-isotropic multi-directional laminate and the effects on transverse shear strength were investigated by conducting experimental tests, CT-scans of the tested specimens and finite element analysis of the critical ply interfaces where delamination is expected to occur. For the latter, a three-

dimensional meso-scale model of the specimen considering transversely isotropic plies and isotropic ply interfaces was implemented in ABAQUS, so that the stress field near the free edges, at the ply interfaces, could be accurately captured at the onset of delamination, before and after resin treatment.

In [4], the same process has been applied to defective laminates to mimic certification conditions, whereby knock-down factors due to defects are usually assessed without suppressing free edge effects. As a result, the effects of the defects on strength are not properly isolated, resulting in incorrect knock-down factor estimations. The treatment successfully suppressed edge effects, resulting in far less conservative strength predictions.

2 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

2.1 Short beam test results

A total of thirteen specimens were manufactured from a 977-2/HTS40 quasi-isotropic laminate, consisting of sixteen plies with the stacking sequence $[\pm 45/0/90_2/0/\mp 45]_s$. The average length, width and thickness of the specimens were 24.2 mm, 8.1 mm and 4.2 mm, respectively. The resin treatment was subsequently applied to seven specimens, with the remaining being left untreated for comparison.

The resin treatment was applied after preparing the lateral surfaces of the specimens using argon plasma. This process ensures a contaminant-free surface so that highly compliant resin can be effectively bonded onto the free edges of the specimens. After pouring EP950G resin into a mould, the treated specimens were cured in an oven and the resin edges were ground back until an average 3.2 mm wide resin block was left on both sides. The full process is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of resin treatment. Specimen dimensions are shown.

The transverse shear strength of both treated and untreated specimens was investigated by following ASTM D2344/D2344M-13 for flat CFRP specimens [5]. The experiments were conducted until ultimate failure occurred, with the displacement of the upper roller of a 3-point bending test rig being controlled by an Instron machine at a rate of 1 mm/min. The ultimate strengths were then computed according to [6]. The average strength and stiffness values along with corresponding standard deviations, before and after treatment, are shown in Table 1. The relative increase in both stiffness and strength after treatment are also shown.

Treatment	Strength [MPa]	% Increase	Stiffness [N/mm]	% Increase
None	79.8 (± 4.4)		5437.2 (± 159.9)	
Resin	102.0 (± 3.1)	+28	6075.8 (± 178.4)	+12

Table 1: Test results of untreated and treated 977-2/HTS40 short beam specimens. Average strength [6] and stiffness are shown, with corresponding standard deviations. The percentage increase in both quantities is also given.

2.2 CT-scans of failed specimens

The treated and untreated specimens were scanned using a Nikon XT H 225 ST CT-scanner, equipped with a Perkin Elmer 1620 16-bit flat panel detector. The settings of 142 kV voltage, 123 μ A and 500 ms of exposure, with an average number of 3141 projections, were used. The software Avizo 9.2.0 was then used for analysis. Ortho-slices of the xz plane were taken near the free edge of the untreated specimens and near the CFRP-resin transition for the treated specimens, so that the influence of the resin treatment on interlaminar damage could be analysed. The location and extent of damage was consistent across samples of the same type, i.e. untreated or treated, so only one scan is shown for each case. In Figure 2a and 2b the untreated and treated specimens are shown, respectively.

In Figure 2a, interlaminar damage is very localised, mostly affecting the 3rd (0/90), 7th (-45/45), 9th (45/-45) and 13th (90/0) interfaces. Less significant damage can also be observed in the 5th (90/0) and 11th (0/90) interfaces, with intralaminar matrix cracking connecting these failed interfaces.

After resin treatment, failure becomes more equally distributed through the thickness of the laminate, resulting in more extensive damage, with multiple ply interfaces failing. This is shown in Figure 2b.

Figure 2: CT ortho-slices in xz plane, near the edge. Damaged ply interfaces are highlighted.

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A finite element model was implemented using ABAQUS Standard software, so that the effects of the treatment on the transverse stress components acting on the interlaminar regions, at failure initiation, could be analysed. In order to accurately capture the complex three-dimensional stress state at the ply interfaces, near the free edge, a very high mesh refinement must be used. As a result, a linear elastic model was implemented, allowing a much greater refinement than conventional non-linear models including material softening, without significantly sacrificing computation runtime. Moreover, the objective of the model is not to obtain ultimate failure predictions but rather understand the influence of the treatment on the individual interlaminar stresses at the point of delamination initiation.

The model pre and post-processing were performed using a Python script and a Fortran user subroutine to generate element outputs (UVARM) was coded for the computation of a delamination initiation index at the ply interfaces, using a quadratic failure criterion [7].

Ply and adjacent interfaces were modelled as separate entities. The former were modelled as 0.25 mm thick transversely isotropic CFRP layers whereas the latter were considered resin rich zones, consisting of 0.016 mm thick isotropic layers with the transverse properties of the composite. These thicknesses were assigned after analysing the untreated specimens under a microscope. The material properties used in the model are shown in Table 2.

Standard linear hexahedral elements (ABAQUS C3D8R elements) with reduced integration and enhanced hourglass control were used. In order to reduce computation runtime, only half of the specimen was modelled by using a symmetry boundary condition in x . Contact between the rollers and the specimen was also replaced by either an applied uniform pressure (replacing the top roller) or Dirichlet boundary conditions, preventing transverse displacement in z (replacing the support rollers). Evidently, the local stresses near these boundary conditions will differ from a model incorporating contact interactions, but the stress field of interest, away from these regions, is similar. The geometry of the model and the location of boundary conditions were implemented according to the aforementioned average measurements of the specimens and the test rig [5].

In the treated case, the same considerations apply with two additional blocks of EP950G resin being added on the sides of the CFRP specimen. The properties of the resin are shown in Table 2.

Composite plies (9772-2/HTS40) [8]		Ply interfaces	Resin edge (EP950G) [9]		
E_{11}	153 GPa	E	10.3 GPa	E	3.8 GPa
E_{22}, E_{33}	10.3 GPa	ν	0.3	ν	0.3
G_{12}, G_{13}	5.2 GPa	Y_T	82 MPa	U_T	65.6 MPa
G_{23}	3.43 GPa	S_L	90 MPa		
ν_{12}, ν_{13}	0.3	S_T	90 MPa		
ν_{23}	0.5				

Table 2: Material properties of composite plies (977-2/HTS40), ply interfaces and resin edge material (EP950G). Y_T , S_L and S_T correspond to transverse tensile and shear strengths for computation of the failure criterion. U_T corresponds to the ultimate tensile strength of EP950G resin.

3.1 Stress singularity and convergence analysis

In the untreated case, high interlaminar stresses develop at certain ply interfaces due to either mismatching shear properties, usually in $\pm\theta$ interfaces, or differing effective Poisson's ratios, usually in 0/90 interfaces [10]. In the former case, the shear stress component τ_{13} is dominant whereas in the latter, the transverse direct stress σ_{33} becomes significant towards the free edge. In both cases, the solution at the free edge from numerical analysis is often unreliable. In typical finite element implementations, these local transverse stresses are theoretically singular, leading to unconverged solutions. Increasing mesh refinement only leads to increased stress values and in the limit, as element size tends to zero, these stresses tend to infinity.

Evidently, delaminations are expected to start from the edges and propagate across the width of the specimen. Consequently, the determination of the stress state at the exact point of initiation becomes

very challenging. Accurate solutions can be obtained, however, at a chosen distance from the free edge by using a minimum number of elements within that distance. Ideally, since the onset of delamination is expected to start at the free edge, it is desired to obtain a converged solution as close to the free edge as possible.

A convergence analysis was performed to ensure accuracy of the solution in every ply interface of the specimen, at a minimum distance of $4\ \mu\text{m}$ away from the free edge. The number of elements along the length, across the width and through the thickness of both fibrous plies and ply interfaces were individually varied until the most computationally inexpensive combination was found whilst respecting the condition above. A total of 83 and 80 elements were used along the length and across the width, respectively. A double mesh bias ratio of a 1000 was used in order to minimise the necessary number of elements across the width, whilst still keeping a very high local mesh refinement near the free edge. Six and three elements through the thickness of each ply and ply interface were used, respectively. A double bias ratio of two was also considered through the thickness of the plies so that outer elements, adjacent to the ply interfaces, have smaller thicknesses.

In the treated case, the same mesh seeding parameters were used along the length and through the thickness of the resin blocks. Across the width, 30 elements with a bias ratio of 600 were used so that the width of the elements of the resin block at the CFRP-resin transition match the width of the adjacent elements of the CFRP section.

3.2 Effects of the treatment

The effects of the treatment on each ply interface can be first analysed at two distances from the edge. In Figure 3a and 3b the square root of the failure index is shown at every interface, approximately $2.7\ \text{mm}$ away from the loading region in x , at $4\ \mu\text{m}$ away from the edge (to guarantee convergence of the solution) and at mid-width, respectively.

The 3rd (0/90), 4th (90/90), 5th (90/0), 7th (-45/45) and 9th (45/-45) interfaces show the highest failure index values before treatment, $4\ \mu\text{m}$ away from the free edge. The treatment affects every ply interface, with the effects being more pronounced near the edge, where the interlaminar transverse stress components become significant and have very large gradients.

Figure 3: Variation of square root of failure index through the thickness of specimen, for both treated and untreated specimens, near the edge ($4\ \mu\text{m}$ away) and at mid-width.

Values taken $2.7\ \text{mm}$ away from loading region in x . Applied load of $2464.1\ \text{N}$.

To illustrate the effect of the resin treatment across the width of the specimen, the variation in maximum square root of the failure index (considering the values at every ply interface) is plotted from a distance of $4\ \mu\text{m}$ away from the free edge to mid-width of the specimen, for both untreated and treated specimens, in Figure 4a. The distance in y is normalised by half of the width of the specimen.

In Figures 4b, 4c and 4d, the variation across the width (starting at 4 μm away from the edge to mid-width) of the relevant stress components at the 3rd (0/90), 4th (90/90) and 9th (45/-45) ply interfaces is shown for both untreated and treated cases. A similar trend is expected in interfaces with a similar combination of adjacent ply orientations, but only these representative cases are shown for brevity. All results were obtained 2.7 mm away from the loading region in the x direction.

From observation of Figures 4b, 4c and 4d, the resin treatment seems to predominantly affect the transverse direct stress σ_{33} near the edges, with the shear stress τ_{13} being less affected. However, the effects on the former quickly dissipate away from the edge, whereas the effects on τ_{13} , despite decreasing as the distance from the edge is increased, generally remain, even at mid-width.

The decreased shear stress τ_{13} at mid-width results in a reduction of the failure index at this location, as shown in Figure 4a. This can also be observed in Figure 3b, with the square root of the failure index being generally smaller at mid-width, after the application of the treatment.

Figure 4: Variation of maximum square root of failure index and of relevant stress components at critical ply interfaces, from 4 μm away from the edge to mid-width. Distance in y is normalised by half-width of the specimen. Values taken 2.7 mm away from loading region in x .

Applied load of 2464.1 N.

4 DISCUSSION

Both experimental and numerical results show the effectiveness of the resin treatment in suppressing interlaminar stress concentrations at the free edges of multi-directional CFRP laminates. The treatment also leads to more widespread damage through the thickness of the laminate, preventing failure localisation in a few critical ply interfaces, as suggested by the CT-scans. This is further supported by the FEA in Figure 3a, with the treatment leading to a more even distribution of the failure indexes through the thickness of the laminate, at 4 μm away from the edge.

It should be noted, however, that the transverse shear strength of a large component is still underpredicted as these stress concentrations are not completely removed, due to the mismatching properties of the CFRP and the material used for the resin treatment.

The effects of the resin treatment can be maximised if resins with similar elastic properties to those of the CFRP matrix are used. The reduced mismatch in properties leads to a decrease in the stress concentrations at the CFRP-resin material transition, improving the effectiveness of the treatment.

The resin block width of ~ 3 mm was selected due to ease of manufacture and constitutes a considerable proportion of the treated specimen. This resulted in a 12% increase of the overall stiffness of the specimen after applying the treatment. As a consequence, the improvement in strength exclusively due to a reduction in edge effects is lower than the total ultimate strength increase reported from the experiments, with some of this increase resulting from the added stiffness. This is also shown in the FE results, as a reduction in the interlaminar shear component τ_{13} led to a reduction in the failure index at mid-width of the specimen, where the effects of the treatment should be non-existent. The corresponding increase in initiation load at mid-width from FEA is approximately 12.3%. This value is, however, considerably smaller than the strength improvement observed near the CFRP-resin transition.

Reducing the width of the resin treatment is desirable, so that edge effects can be effectively suppressed whilst preventing an increase in the overall stiffness of the specimen. In this work, even with the effect of added stiffness, the strength of the treated specimen is still below the expected strength of a large component without exposed free edges, as failure still starts prematurely at the CFRP-resin transition. However, if a stiffer resin with similar properties to the CFRP matrix is used, the width of the resin blocks should be reduced to avoid considerable stiffening effects and consequent strengthening of the specimen over the actual strength of the final component.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Experimental and numerical results showed significant strength improvements in transverse shear strength of CFRP laminates after applying a resin edge treatment on the exposed free edges of short beam specimens. The treatment effectively suppresses stress concentrations at the edges, increasing the strength by 28% in the cases tested in this work. CT-scans also showed that the treatment leads to a more widespread damage pattern through the thickness of the laminate and prevents failure localisation at ply interfaces with very high interlaminar stresses. However, the stress concentrations at the edges were not completely removed, mainly due to the mismatching properties of the resin used for the treatment and the CFRP matrix. In this case, the effectiveness of the treatment can be improved by utilising a stiffer resin for the treatment, but the width of the resin blocks should be minimised to prevent over-stiffening of the specimen.

The treatment can be implemented in the certification process of aerospace structures to produce less conservative transverse shear strength predictions of large components, without adding any significant costs.

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